

SPECIAL APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING TOLERANCE IN PEDAGOGICAL PROCESSES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14900321>

Annotation: This article discusses in detail the origin of the word tolerance, types of tolerance, special intercultural, person-oriented, cooperation-based, ethical-cultural, conflictological, reflexive approaches to developing tolerance in pedagogical processes.

Keywords: tolerance, person, culture, ethical-cultural, conflictological approach, reflexive approach.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada tolerantlik soʻzining kelib chiqishi, tolerantlikning tiplari, tolerantlikni pedagogik jarayonlarda rivojlantirish uchun maxsus madaniyatlararo, shaxsga yoʻnaltirilgan, hamkorlikka asoslangan, axloqiy-madaniy, konfliktologik, refleksiv yondashuvlar haqida batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: tolerantlik, shaxs, madaniyat, axloqiy-madaniy, konfliktologik yondashuv, refleksiv yondashuv.

Аннотация: В статье подробно рассматривается происхождение слова толерантность, типы толерантности и конкретные межкультурные, лично-ориентированные, коллаборативные, этико-культурные, конфликтологические и рефлексивные подходы к развитию толерантности в педагогических процессах.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, личность, культура, этико-культурный, конфликтологический подход, рефлексивный подход.

The word tolerance is derived from the Latin word (tolerantia), which means patience. The meaning and nature of tolerance are interpreted in similar ways by different peoples. For example, in Spanish - a way of recognizing an opinion that differs from one's own; in French - allowing others to think or act differently than you; in English - to be patient, kind; in Chinese - to be forgiving, kind, noble towards others; in Arabic - to be forgiving, merciful, gentle, kind, merciful, noble, patient; in Russian - to be patient towards something or someone, to be patient, to be patient; to tolerate something or someone, to consider the opinion of another, to be kind; in Uzbek - to be open-minded towards others, to be kind to the lifestyle, character, customs, feelings, thoughts, ideas and beliefs of others, etc.[1]

Indeed, if we look at the etymology of this word, the truly human meaning of the expression tolerance in social relations corresponds to like-mindedness, solidarity, and practical interpersonal communication. The theoretical and practical application of the term tolerance is based on the definition given in the 1995 “Declaration of Principles of Tolerance”. This document states: Tolerance means respecting, accepting and correctly understanding the rich variety of cultures in our world. The diverse ways of expressing oneself and demonstrating human uniqueness. It is created by knowledge, sincerity, open communication, and freedom of thought, conscience, and belief.[2] Tolerance is unity in diversity. This is not only a moral duty, but also a political and legal necessity. Tolerance is what makes it possible to achieve peace and leads from the culture of warlessness to the culture of peace.[3]

There are the following types of tolerance: gender, age, education, interethnic, racial, religious, geographical, interclass, physiological, political, marginal. In the current conditions of globalization, tolerance should be considered a necessary condition for cultural development. Intolerance has always existed in human history and has caused wars. Religious persecution and ideological conflicts have led to fanaticism, insults, and violations of the rights to life. In such conditions, it has always been necessary to educate the people in the spirit of tolerance. The meaning that follows from this is that tolerance is the basis of a person’s worldview and helps to actively influence the constructive consciousness of citizens and stability in the country.

If we look back, we can safely claim that Uzbekistan has been a land of tolerance throughout its three thousand-year history, and we have every reason to say that this virtue in the minds and consciousness of people actually emerged in Transoxiana, and we have the right to be proud of it.[4] The fact that our ancestors in the past, such as Al-Farabi, Al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, Bukhari, Amir Temur, Navoi, and Babur, were extremely humane and kind-hearted individuals is proof of this.

Specific approaches to developing tolerance in pedagogical processes and their detailed description are as follows:

1. Intercultural approach - this approach is based on recognizing cultural diversity and making it an integral part of the educational process. It develops a sense of respect for other cultures and national traditions in students.

2. Person-centered approach - based on educational principles and requires taking into account the individual needs, experiences and interests of each student.

3. Collaborative approach - based on developing students' ability to work together and strengthening their mutual understanding. This approach emphasizes the use of group activities to develop tolerance.

4. Moral-cultural approach - this approach is aimed at developing tolerance through the formation of moral and spiritual values. It changes not only the behavior of students, but also their internal culture.

5. Conflictological approach - this approach is aimed at teaching the skills of effective conflict management and resolution in developing tolerance.

6. The reflexive approach is based on developing tolerance through reflection, that is, on developing students' ability to self-analyze and evaluate their own relationships.[6]

In conclusion, it should be said that it helps future social workers to master new approaches and be prepared to work effectively with diverse groups. Continuous improvement of educational processes aimed at developing tolerance will serve to make not only students, but also society more stable and graceful in solving social problems.

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